

Correlation of Peripheral Blood Smear, RBC Indices, and RBC Histogram in the Diagnosis of Anaemia

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Abstract:

Background: In haematological disorders morphological changes in RBCs plays a vital role. The RBCs indices were always correlated with peripheral smear findings. This study was done to understand the importance of histogram and peripheral smear findings.

Materials and Methods: EDTA blood sample from patients of anemia was run on Nihon Kohden Five part automated cell counter and peripheral smears were prepared for 3 months in tertiary hospital. The correlation between microscopic findings in RBCs morphology with cell counter histograms was done.

Result: Total 176 patients of anemia were studied. The females were 130 (73.86%) and males were 46 (26.17%). Microcytic hypochromic anemia was common and was seen in 64.77% followed by Normochromic normocytic anemia which was seen in 19.31%, Dimorphic anemia in 11.93%, Macrocytic anemia in 2.84%, and Pancytopenia in 1.13%. In microcytic anemia the curve was shifted to left, in macrocytic anemia the shift was towards right side, and dimorphic anemia shows bimodal peak.

Conclusion: For diagnosis of anemia peripheral smear findings were definitive and histogram can be used as supplementary tool.

Keywords: Histogram RBC, Anaemia Peripheral Smear.

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Introduction

A histogram is crucial for accurately diagnosing anemia morphologically. MCV and RDW were crucial for morphological interpretation among other indicators. [1,2] The distribution of red blood cells follows a bell-shaped curve that peaks in 80–100 feet. The curve was broader for a heterogeneous population of cells and smaller for a homogeneous population. Due to macrocytes, the curve was pushed to the right in megaloblastic anemia and to the left in microcytic anemia. Dimorphic anemia is the term for morphologically two red cell population, in which numerous peaks can be visible, if the patient had undergone treatment. In these circumstances RDW was a more accurate measure of anisocytosis than MCV. [3,4] A higher RDW indicates the presence of two distinct populations of cells: immature red blood cells that were larger than usual, and small and some normalized cells. [5]

Materials and Methods

Patients were studied during this period. Every anemic patient who visited the haematology section had their red blood cell histograms examined in an effort to establish a relationship between the results

of the peripheral smear and the histogram. The Nihon Kohden 5-part automated haematology analyzer provided a complete blood count and a histogram. Examining peripheral smears was also performed.

1. In microcytosis, the RBC graph started before 34 fl and again reached to baseline before 150 fl and referred as shift to left.
2. While in macrocytosis there was right shift where the graph started after 34 fl and reached to baseline after 150 fl.

The graph's beginning at 34 feet and ending between 225 and 250 feet were regarded as its broad bases. Due to the presence of dimorphic cells, the RBC graph in dimorphic anemia displayed two peaks. The graph would be constrained and show a brief peak if the population of red blood cells had a single lineage. Utilizing SPSS 22 for data analysis, the P-value was computed by combining degree of freedom and chi-square. P values of less than 0.05 were regarded as statistically significant.

Inclusion Criteria: All cases with haemoglobin below 11 gm/dl were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Patient having leukemoid reaction, leukemia were excluded.

Results

In our study of histograms of various types of anemia total 176 cases were studied.

This study included predominantly 130 (73.86%) females and 46 (26.17%) males. Maximum number of anemia cases was noted in 30-40 years of age range (Table 1). All cases had hemoglobin less than 11 gm/dl. Cases were consisted of Normocytic normochromic anemia, Microcytic hypochromic anemia, dimorphic anemia and pancytopenia which were diagnosed by peripheral smear.

In our study 34 (19.31%) cases were normocytic normochromic anemia, 114 (64.77%) cases were of microcytic hypochromic anemia, 5 (2.84%) cases were of macrocytic anemia and 21(11.93%) cases were of dimorphic anemia. Pancytopenia was seen in 02 (1.13%) cases (Table 2).

In our study of 176 cases, 28(15.907%) cases showed normal curve, left shift were seen in 52(29.54%) cases, right shift in 09 (5.11%) cases, broad base in 68 (38.63) cases, short peak in 07 (3.97%) cases and bimodal curve in 12(6.82%) cases (Table 3). In Normochromic Normocytic anemia MCV, MCH, MCHC and RDW were within normal limits.

MCV, MCH were decreased in Hypochromic Microcytic anemia with increased RDW and increased MCV, MCH, RDW with normal MCHC was seen in Macrocytic anemia MCV, MCH, MCHC were within normal limits and RDW was increased due to high degree of anisopoikilocytosis in Dimorphic anemia In pancytopenia only change noticed in red cell indices are increased RDW with normal MCV, MCH, and MCHC.

In our study out of 34(19.31%) cases of Normocytic Normochromic anemia, 21(11.93%) cases showed normal curve and 13(7.38) % showed broad base curve. Of the 114 instances of microcytic hypochromic anemia (64.77%), 4

(2.27%) had a normal distribution, 59 (33.52%) had a shift to the left, 44 (25%) had a broad base curve, 4 (2.27%) had a bimodal curve, and 3 (1.71%) had a short peak. Dimorphic anemia was found in 21 (11.93%) patients overall. Of those cases, 2 (1.13%) had a normal curve, 1 (0.56%) had a left curve, 7 (3.97%) had a right curve, 2 (1.13%) had a broad base curve, and 9 (5.11%) had a bimodal curve. The macrocytic anemia cases, all five (2.84%) had a right shift curve. Table 4 shows that all pancytopenia cases had broad base curves. A chi square score of 70.14 and a P value of less than 0.001 were deemed statistically significant (Table 4).

Discussion

The RBC histogram was generated in automated Haematology analyser depending upon the particle size.

Information about RBC parameters like RDW, MCH and MCV. 1,2 were obtained which helped in diagnosis and typing of anemia.

Normal curve was symmetrical bell shaped or showed Gaussian distribution. Normal curve shows MCV range between 80-100 fl. [6-8] RBC histograms in the cell counter counts only those cells as RBCs who have volume sizes between 36 fl to 360 fl. Those cells counted in the range 24 fl to 36 fl were rejected and not included in the RBC count

The presence of tiny particles such as microspherocytes, platelet clumping, elliptocytes, normoblast, malaria parasite, etc. was the reason why the RBC graph began below 36 fl. [9]. The RBC histogram was created using the Coulter principle, which counts and sizes red blood cells. The conductivity of the cells changed as they passed through the aperture. [10] An electrical pulse is produced as a result of the change in conductance, and the amplitude of this pulse is proportional to the cell volume. [11,12]

There was a shift in conductance as the cells passed through the aperture. [10]. An electrical pulse with an amplitude proportionate to the cell volume is produced by the change in conductance. [11,12].

Table 1: Age and sex wise distribution of anemia

Age in yrs	10- 20	21- 30	31 -40	41 -50	51- 60	Total
Total	07	39	82	32	16	176
Percentage	3.97	22.15	46.59	18.18	9.19	100
Male	03	15	19	14	05	46
Female	04	24	63	18	09	130
M : F						

Table 2: Cases in different anemias

Types of anemia	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
Hypochromic Microcytic Anemia	114	64.77
Normochromic Normocytic	34	19.31
Macrocytic	05	2.84
Dimorphic	21	11.93
Pancytopenia	02	1.13
Total	176	100

Table 3: Types of histogram abnormality

Types of histogram	No. of cases	Percentage
Normal Curve	28	15.90
Left shift	52	29.54
Right Shift	09	5.11
Broad Base	68	38.63
Bimodal	12	6.82
Short peak	07	3.97

Table 4: RBC histogram variations in different anemia

	Normal Curve	Left shift	Right shift	Broad Base	Bimodal	Short peak
Normocytic	21(11.93%)	-	-	13(7.38%)	-	-
Microcytic	04 (2.27%)	59(33.52%)	-	44 (25%)	04(2.27%)	03(1.70%)
Macrocytic	-	-	05(2.84%)	-	-	-
Dimorphic	02(1.13%)	01(0.56%)	07(3.97%)	02(1.13%)	09(5.11%)	-
Pancytopenia	-	-	-	02(1.13%)	-	-

P value < 0.001, Chi Square Value -70.14

Table 5: Comparative study of anemia based on peripheral smear

Anemia	Sandhya et al(%)	Jitendra Chavda et al(%)	Byna Syam Sundara Rao et al(%)	Present study (%)
Normocytic Anemia	17	17.4	19.4	19.31
Microcytic	61	65	63.63	64.77
Macrocytic	03	3.6	2.2	2.84
Dimorphic	15	14	12.7	11.93
Pancytopenia	03	-	1.8	1.13

Table 6: Comparative study of histogram curves

Type of histogram	Sandhya et al (%)	Jitendra Chavda et al (%)	Byna Syam Sundara Rao et al (%)	Present study (%)
Curve	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)
Normocytic anemia	15	19	17.7	15.90
Left shift	30	27	29.0	29.54
Right Shift	06	07	5.45	5.11
Broad Base	40	38	37.72	38.63
Bimodal	04	03	7.27	6.82
Short peak	05	06	2.7	3.97

Reticulocytosis is typically associated with right-sided shoulder, while red cell agglutination is associated with erythrocyte population flagging on the extreme right of the histogram.

In 114 instances (64.77%) of our investigation, hypochromic microcytic anemia was the most common finding. 34 patients (19.31%) had normochromic normocytic anemia. Five patients (2.84%) had macrocytic anemia, while twenty-one patients (11.93%) had dimorphic anemia. Pancytopenia seen in 2 (1.13%) of the cases.

Sandhya et al. (2014), Chavda et al. (2015) and BynaSyam Sundara Rao et al (2017) in their studies also found similar distribution of anemia cases (Table 5). In our study broad base was observed in 68 patients, left shift was seen in 52 patients, normal curve in 28 patients followed by right shift in 09 patients, while short peak was noted in 07 patients. RBC indices were normal in normochromic normocytic anemia. High RDW was seen when there was marked anisocytosis. In our study out of 34(19.31%) cases of normocytic

normochromic anemia, 21(11.93%) showed normal curve and 13(7.38) % cases showed broad base curve.

These finding were correlated with study carried by Chavda J. and Bynasyam Sundara Rao et al. MCV and MCH were decreased in microcytic hypochromic anemia but MCHC was normal. RBC with low MCV had shown shift to left. [12,13] High RDW and broad base curve was due to anisocytosis. In hypochromic microcytic anemia as there was micocytosis and RDW was increased. On peripheral smear also, hypochromic microcytic anemia showed anisopoikilocytosis. Out of 114 (64.77%) cases of microcytic hypochromic anemia, 04(2.27%) cases were normal, 59 (33.52%) cases.

These results were linked to research done by Sandhya [4] and Chavda J. [5]. The low red cell count and hemoglobin levels were positively linked with the short peak. The histogram may show two or more red cell populations in dimorphic anemia, however in dual populations, the histogram showed two different red cell populations.

Two populations of red blood cells—microcytic and normocytic or normocytic and macrocytic—or a mixture of small, normal, and large cells of varying sizes, as well as a mixture of donor and patient red blood cells, may be seen in a dimorphic blood image. MCV, MCH, and MCHC in our dimorphic anemia study were all normal; however there was a noticeable rise in RDW because of anisopoikilocytosis.

The macrocytic anemia cases, all five (2.84%) had a right shift curve. This result was connected with Sandhya and colleagues. [4] The right shift curve was connected with higher MCV and MCH. All cases of pancytopenia showed a Borad base curve, which was consistent with the findings of the Sandhya et al. [4] study. The histogram proved to be a valuable tool in the diagnosis of anemia when paired with RBC indices.

Conclusion

In addition to peripheral smears, histograms are useful in the diagnosis of illnesses affecting RBCs. Analyzers for haematology was incredibly helpful and trustworthy when assessing abnormal peripheral smears.

In nearly all peripheral smear interpretations of anemic cases, the histogram was correlated (p value <0.001, chi square value 70.14). The majority of

cases demonstrate a strong correlation between the PS findings and the histogram; nonetheless, the histogram should only be utilized for screening purposes.

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